

Keep Dangerous People Away from Pandemic Pathogens

By Steven Quay, Stephen Massey, and David Hermiz

Current regulations fail to adequately screen for high-risk personality disorders in laboratory scientists and staff working with the deadliest pathogens on the planet. Currently, these disorders are most likely to be identified retrospectively if there is a purposeful release of a pathogen from a laboratory. The existing regulatory framework, under the Federal Select Agent Program (FSAP), needs to be updated to exclude individuals with high-risk personality disorders before we have another event like the 2001 anthrax poisoning or the COVID-19 pandemic.

The FSAP, established after the Twin Towers attack in September 2001 and the mailing of deadly anthrax spores to Federal government offices in October of the same year, is managed by the Centers for Disease Control (CDC) and the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA). The FSAP oversees the “possession, use, or transfer” of sixty-eight viruses, bacteria, or toxins that have been determined to have the “potential to pose a severe threat to public health and safety.”

In 2022, there were 234 entities registered, and 8,516 individuals approved to work with Select Agents. Also in 2022, there were 170 reports of the release of a Select Agent from one of these entities and six reports of the loss of a Select Agent. Fortunately, none of these containment breaches led to illness or death.

The Biosecurity Risk Assessment Group, a program within the FBI, has the responsibility for performing the Security Risk Assessment for individuals applying for the FSAP. This currently involves an electronic records check only. In 2022, sixteen individuals were denied access to Select Agents because they were “restricted persons” as defined by Congress. A restricted person is one indicted or convicted of a serious crime, a fugitive, an illegal alien, a person with a dishonorable military discharge, or “adjudicated as a mental defective or has been committed to any mental institution.”

Of the sixteen individuals denied access to Select Agents because of a determination they were Restricted Persons, eleven were denied because of a criminal conviction, three were illegal aliens, one was using a controlled substance, and one was adjudicated as a mental defective.

The term mental defective is an outdated term found elsewhere in legislation, including ATF law on gun ownership. It has been interpreted to include “persons who are found incompetent to stand trial or not guilty by reason of mental disease or defect, lack of mental responsibility, or insanity, and that the term includes persons found guilty but mentally ill.”

Given that gun ownership is a Second Amendment right of all citizens, it is understandable that restrictions based on well documented mental health disorders should require extensive evidence and strong justification. In contrast, there is no such equivalent right to work with deadly pathogens, even though they can be more deadly than firearms. Therefore, we advocate for the implementation of more rigorous psychiatric clearance protocols and elevated standards of mental health fitness for individuals who work with dangerous pathogens.

Among the group of high-risk personality disorders, antisocial personality disorder (ASPD) is the most associated with dangerous behaviors and criminal activity. ASPD is an established diagnosis in both the DSM-5 and ICD-11, recognized within the United States and internationally. The diagnosis of ASPD can be accurately and reliably established through a comprehensive psychiatric evaluation. This evaluation may

include psychological testing, such as the Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory (MMPI), which is validated for accuracy and precision.

ASPD is characterized by a pervasive and stable pattern of behavior, thoughts and inner experiences that typically begin in adolescence or early adulthood and that deviate significantly from societal norms. The disorder is characterized by traits such as aggressiveness, lack of guilt or remorse, failure to adhere to legal and ethical norms, incapacity for mutually intimate relationships, impulsivity, risk-taking, and egocentrism.

One perspective on the diagnosis of ASPD is juridical, with the antisocial label often applied retrospectively to individuals who break the law. However, this perspective can be limiting as criminal activity is not a necessary criterion for ASPD diagnosis; the disorder can be identified through a broader pattern of disregard for the rights of others and societal norms, which can be identified through a comprehensive psychiatric evaluation.

The problem with limiting the definition of a restricted person for purposes of working with Select Agents to only people who have committed a serious crime is that you miss the much larger group of individuals who are predisposed to commit serious crimes, including purposely releasing a Select Agent into the community.

In 2022, for example, only 0.1% of the individuals applying for Select Agent research positions were criminals. But if we apply the prevalence of ASPD from the general population, about 2% overall, we would expect to find 170 scientists or staff currently working with Select Agents that would meet criteria for ASPD, a high risk personality disorder, in which a purposeful release into the community is a real possibility.

The FBI's suspect in the 2001 release of anthrax (a Select Agent) from a CDC laboratory, who committed suicide shortly after learning he was about to be indicted, was identified only in retrospect as having a high-risk personality disorder. During the investigation of the event, which killed five people and injured dozens of others, a government investigative panel, the Expert Behavioral Analysis Panel, issued a report in March 2011 which detailed the suspect's mental health issues. According to the panel's report, the Army did not examine the suspect's background adequately before clearing him to work with anthrax, and such clearance should not have been given. This is the missed opportunity we propose to remedy.

The Federal Select Agent Program controls access to the sixty-eight of the deadliest pathogens and toxins on the planet. Congress should amend the law authorizing the FSAP to keep these pandemic-enabling pathogens out of the hands of dangerous individuals by screening for high-risk personality disorders that can predict who is predisposed to purposefully causing a pandemic. Deadly pathogens and toxins are bipartisan killers.

Authors

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